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**TRANSFORMING SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: THE BEARING OF COOPERATIVE
LEARNING STRATEGY ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN UPPER-BASIC SCHOOLS IN
DELTA STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This research examined how social studies instruction is changing in Delta State, Nigeria, with an emphasis on how the cooperative learning approach affects students' academic achievement in upper-basic schools. The research targeted Upper-basic 9 (JSS3) Social Studies students in the Delta North Senatorial District and used a quasi-experimental design with pre and post-test experimental and control groups. Six schools were picked at random using a multi-stage sampling technique that included balloting and purposeful sampling, yielding an overall sample size of 720. A research sample of 504 was determined by using 70% of this sample. A teacher-made social studies exam (TMTSS) with fifty objective questions that matched certain themes from the JSS3 social studies scheme of work for the second term was used in the research. Social Studies experts and members of Delta State University's Department of Social Science Education validated the instrument's face and content. A t-test was used to test the hypothesis, and descriptive statistics like the mean and standard deviation addressed the research question. The outcomes showed that Delta State students taking Upper-basic Social Studies by conventional method in secondary school did worse than those using the cooperative learning Strategy. It was recommended that to inspire students to participate more actively in their social studies education, Upper-basic Social Studies teachers should include entertaining and engaging activities in their courses, such as the use of cooperative learning method.

Keywords: Transforming, Cooperative Learning Strategy, Academic Performance, Social Studies Education

Introduction

One of the learning techniques that students believe is appropriate for achieving successful learning outcomes is teamwork. Cooperative learning, also known as an approach to learning, is a method of teaching/learning in which students collaborate in groups to solve problems, finish tasks, or produce a product. When it has to do with classroom learning, the idea of collaboration describes how students collaborate in small groups to complete a task that is structured. It requires that students take responsibility for their work plus the group's work, which might be evaluated to ascertain the notch to which each member of the group and the individual have attained the necessary knowledge and skills and have met the learning objectives (Kayes & Kayes, 2011). Consequently, cooperation might be a useful tool for inspiring students, promoting engaged learning, and fostering the progress of critical thinking, communication, and decision-making abilities. MeQuerrey's (2017) research findings served as the foundation for the case for implementing cooperation in the classroom. "Teamwork encourages cooperative communication," according to MeQuerrey's (2017) findings. MeQuerrey (2017) originated that teaching children to work in crews gives them the basic capacities needed to function as a cohesive unit toward a common

objective. MeQuerrey (2017) further claimed that this kind of cooperation teaches children a range of skills including communication, compromise, and collective effect that will be useful for them later in the workforce. According to Firestone (2017) research, learning outcomes are amplified when students collaborate as a crew. According to Firestone (2017), collaboration fosters effective learning, which implies that it might have a good bearing on academic achievement.

Teamwork in education represents a learning approach that promotes a learner-centered methodology. In the framework of classroom collaboration, Fredrick (2008) defines Cooperative learning Strategy as a classroom-based cooperative initiative. He observed that implementing this strategy during classroom instruction contributes to the progression of students' social skills. Fredrick contends that in a classroom where teamwork is emphasized in teaching/learning, students gain the aptitude to assert themselves in shaping the content learned. According to Fredrick (2008), the Cooperative Learning Strategy empowers learners to take responsibility for their own learning and derive meaningful insights from the material being studied.

The crux of teamwork, as described above, underscores cooperation in grasping a particular topic or theme within a given subject. This implies that students must work collectively to maximize their individual and collective learning experiences, a notion supported by Marchetty (2018). Marchetty advocates for the assignment of learners into groups by the class teacher as a commendable teaching approach that enhances the effectiveness of instruction. Marchetty asserted that Cooperative learning involves students collaborating in small, identifiable groups, fostering the progression of critical thinking skills. Marchetty found that this strategy facilitates the exchange of knowledge among students, enhancing their aptitude to grasp the material under review. Furthermore, Marchetty (2018) exposed that the Cooperative learning concept encourages students to showcase their expertise on the subject, leading to an upsurge in learning, reading habits, and motivation. According to Marchetty's (2018) research, this approach has demonstrated an improvement in students' attitudes toward learning. The author's observations suggest that Cooperative learning implies group or team learning, involving cooperative efforts to understand a specified material.

Decuyper et al. (2010) have conceptualized cooperative learning to denote the cooperative course aimed at achieving a shared objective within a group. The authors apply this concept to the realm of learning, emphasizing that the strategy enables members of a class or group to exchange knowledge and complement each other's skills. However, they underscore that successful implementation of these strategies necessitates a high level of commitment from all crew members to accomplish the objectives outlined in the instructional materials. Their observation highlights that the skiving of commitment and effort from crew members might lead to failure in the cooperative learning course. In a broader sense, a group of learners refers to students working collectively on an assignment with the common goal of achievement. Groups typically have defined membership and engage in a set of activities. In the framework of education, these activities revolve around the learning of assigned topics essential for meeting a specified objective. While each member bears individual responsibility for contributing to the crew, the collective success of the group rests on the shoulders of the entire crew (Decuyper et al., 2010).

Kayes and Kayes (2011) underscored the significance of the Crew Learning concept, noting its inherent advantages in the learning course. Kayes and Kayes research made bare a dynamic course inherent in this learning model, suggesting that Crew Learning represents a shift from individual learning to a cooperative approach that forms the basis for transitioning from individual to organizational learning. The authors argue that Lineup Learning, when implemented, has the potential to foster increased interest in learning, enhance interactive skills among class members, and improve communication skills. Applying this strategy to Social Studies education is particularly ideal, given that the nature of Social Studies often

necessitates the exploration of basic themes through cooperative learning methods such as Team Learning, where ideas are subjected to debate and analysis.

Furthermore, the University of Marlborough (2019) identified four major benefits of collaboration for student progression and success. According to their findings, participating in team activities aids in the progression of crucial communication and collaboration skills, preparing students for success both inside and outside the classroom. The outlined benefits of collaboration for learning include:

1. Teachers' essential social skill
2. Improves self – confidence
3. Reduces bully
4. Sets students up for future success.

The aforementioned benefits derived from exposing students to the team-learning strategy are directly linked to the learning objectives of Social Studies, as outlined by Osakwe and Itedjere (2005). These objectives involve fostering the critical thinking skills of students. Moreover, the goalmouth of Social Studies educators is to equip their students with effective social skills, instil a strong sense of self-confidence, create a conducive environment for teacher-learner relationships in the classroom, and guide the student body toward improved academic performance. This implies that the team-learning strategy significantly influences the learning outcomes of students. Therefore, the introduction of this strategy in the teaching/learning of Social Studies is a highly favourable progression. The implication is that, when appropriately employed and embraced as a teaching strategy by educators, it has the potential to yield high performance in the subject area under consideration.

Statement of the Problem

In the context of upper-basic schools in Delta State, Nigeria, there exists a noticeable deficiency in the current approach to Social Studies education. Observations indicate a lack of effective instructional methodologies, leading to suboptimal academic performance among students in this subject. The prevailing traditional teaching methods are often rigid, relying on rote memorization and passive learning, which may not adequately engage students or foster a deep understanding of the subject matter. This inadequacy in the current educational approach has far-reaching consequences. Students may struggle to develop critical thinking skills, analytical abilities, and a comprehensive understanding of the societal and historical contexts presented in Social Studies. As a result, there is a risk of diminished academic performance, hindering the overall educational attainment of students in upper-basic schools. Furthermore, the failure to equip students with a nuanced understanding of social issues may impede their ability to actively participate in civic life and contribute meaningfully to their communities.

A transformative shift towards the implementation of cooperative learning strategies in Social Studies education holds the promise of numerous benefits. By fostering collaborative learning environments, students are likely to experience increased engagement, enhanced critical thinking, and improved retention of information. Cooperative learning encourages active participation, peer interaction, and the development of social skills, creating a conducive atmosphere for the exploration of complex social issues.

In resolving the observed problem, the potential benefits include elevated academic performance, a deeper comprehension of social concepts, and the cultivation of a generation of students equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary for informed civic engagement. Moreover, a successful integration of cooperative learning strategies could contribute to the overall improvement of the educational landscape in Delta State, fostering a positive impact on both

individual students and the broader community. Hence, this study on transforming social studies education: the bearing of cooperative learning strategy on academic performance in upper-basic schools in delta state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The ultimate objective of this research is to investigate cooperative learning strategy on academic performance in social studies education in schools in Delta State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research is carried out to fulfil the following objectives.

1. To investigate the disparity in academic performance between Upper-basic Social Studies students instructed through conventional methods and those taught using the cooperative learning strategy in Delta State.

Research Question

This research question serves as a guiding query for the research:

1. What disparity exist in the academic performances of Upper-basic Social Studies students instructed through conventional methods compared to those taught with the cooperative learning strategy in Delta State?

Hypothesis

The research presents a null hypothesis to be tested at a significant level of 0.05:

1. There is no significant difference in the academic achievements of Upper-basic Social Studies students when comparing those instructed through conventional methods with those taught using the cooperative learning strategy in Delta State.

Literature Review

Cooperative learning Strategy (TLS) has demonstrated positive outcomes on students' learning, leading to its widespread adoption in various disciplines as a transformative teaching method. In the research conducted by Cheng et al. (2013), the effectiveness of Team-Based Learning (TBL) was highlighted across multiple disciplines. The authors describe TLS as an instructor-led, learner-centered approach with functions akin to problem-based learning, yet more cost-effective. Their findings indicate that this strategy enhances the learning behaviours of students, as evidenced by improved scores in final examinations, such as in the case of nursing students undergoing a material-child nursing course.

The research concludes that the design of Team Learning Strategies necessitates out-of-class preparation before each session, fostering active and self-directed learning. Additionally, Team-Based Learning provides opportunities for learner-to-learner interactions, promoting active engagement and cooperation among students. The authors note that this strategy enhances students' class engagement, collaboration values, and overall academic performance. Importantly, the research suggests that the adoption of TLS has a particularly significant bearing on academically weaker students, making it a valuable tool for Social Studies teaching/learning. The strategy's potential aligns well with the objectives of the Social Studies course, making it a suitable and effective approach for achieving the intended outcomes.

The research conducted by Seyedeh et al. (2018) concurred that there is a bearing on learning outcomes attributed to the cooperative learning strategy. The authors investigated the effects of team-based learning on learning outcomes in a rheumatology course. The variables examined in their research encompassed student engagement, account aptitude, satisfaction, and the preference for team-based learning over traditional lecture methods. Additionally, the research evaluated

the influence of Team-Based Learning (TBL) on knowledge retention and application over time, specifically focusing on short answer questions based on clinical scenarios related to history-taking and diagnostic skills in medical students.

A quasi-experimental approach was utilized in the study, which involved 84 third-year medical students enrolled in a rheumatic study at Shariati Hospital, a teaching hospital located at Tehran University of Medical Sciences. The traditional lecture-based strategy was contrasted with the Team-Based Understanding (TBU) approach.

In addition, the authors used the Team-Based Learning Students' Evaluation Instrument (TBLSA) and the Classroom Involvement Survey (CES) to perform an evaluation after implementing team-based learning. Using short-answer questions about rheumatic disorders, the assessment of knowledge utilization was done three times. Student t-tests and repeated analysis of variance (RM-ANOVA) with SPSS software version 16 were used to compare the results. Higher levels of student satisfaction, engagement, and long-term learning using Team-Based Learning (TBL) were revealed by the research. These results support the importance of the team-learning approach since it fosters higher academic achievement. Thus, in order to improve their pupils' academic performance, social studies teachers should think about implementing this tactic, provided they possess the knowledge to construct a team-learning classroom model.

To provide a good cooperative learning experience, the need of classroom management is stressed. Students may create units based on acquaintances or common interests rather than experiencing the genuine advantages of meaningful teamwork if professors don't take the effort to organize the groups or teams. As a result, in order to strategically assign groups so that every student has a relevant learning experience, teachers must have a thorough grasp of their pupils. Selma et al. (2013) provided integrated models and provided evidence for the notion that team learning incorporates a contextualized model. This implies that successful team learning is a result of intentional teaching aimed at improving interaction skills, ensuring the inclusion of every class member in the pursuit of enhanced learning outcomes. The research by Offenbech (2001) proposed that the team-learning model comprises a group size of 3-5 individuals, specific or identified classroom activities, an assessment of student attitudes toward the task, the extent of team learning, and the team's performance. These elements are crucial characteristics and procedures to consider when constructing a cooperative learning strategy model.

The University of Bath (2020) highlights the importance of team-based learning as a powerful kind of peer learning while contextualizing the use of the cooperative learning strategy model. As part of the technique, students are placed in a team-based learning setting and given homework assignments to complete before class. The homework assignments are then examined both individually and collaboratively during the session. Students then take part in group activities where they apply their knowledge. The model's foundation is the need for curriculum reform, which includes implementing cutting-edge teaching and learning techniques as well as course review examinations. The current state of education presents the school system with a fantastic chance to investigate and put into practice tactics that include pupils in cooperative teaming and peer learning. The way the teams are initially set up has a big impact on how well these dynamics work.

- a. As outlined by Michelson (2020), teachers must grasp the fundamental principles and the desired sequence of events when implementing a team learning class. This involves utilizing the Team Learning Strategy and constructing a learning model based on identified engagement principles. The research by Michelson highlights four key principles in this model:
- b. Proper Formation and Management of Groups: Under this model, groups must be meticulously formed and managed to enable them to effectively carry out assigned tasks. This includes lessening barricades to group cohesiveness and providing the necessary resources.

- c. Account aptitude of Students: A distinction is drawn between traditional classes and team learning in terms of student account aptitude. In traditional classes, account aptitude is often established through grade assignments since students are primarily accountable to the instructor. In team learning, however, fostering cohesive learning teams requires assessing various aspects of student behavior. Students must be held accountable for individually preparing for cluster work, dedicating time and effort to completing group assignments, and engaging with each other productively.
- d. Team Assignments for Learning and Team Progression: Designing appropriate group assignments is a crucial element in successfully implementing team learning. Michelson emphasizes that many reported problems with learning clusters stem from inappropriate cluster assignments. According to the model, effective team assignments should genuinely necessitate cluster interaction. Assignments requiring clusters to make verdicts and report them in a simplified form tend to generate high levels of group interaction. On the other hand, assignments involving complex outputs, such as lengthy documents or oral presentations, might lead to clusters dividing the work, limiting intra-group interaction, and hindering inter-group comparisons.
- e. Students must Receive Frequent and Immediate Feedback

Methodology

This research employed a quasi-experimental design, utilizing pre-test and post-test assessments for both the treatment and control groups. The study design encompassed a structured framework involving pre-test and post-test assessments, along with the establishment of both experimental and control groups. The dependent variable under scrutiny was academic performance, while the independent variable was the implementation of the cooperative learning strategy. To guide the research, one research question and one hypothesis were formulated.

The research targeted Upper-basic 9 (JSS3) Social Studies students in Public Schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State, Nigeria, encompassing 161 schools with a student population of 14,952. The researcher employed a multi-stage sampling approach, involving balloting, purposive sampling, and the use of appropriate percentages to select a proportionate number of students. Six schools were sampled, resulting in a participant size of 720, from which 70 percent was adopted to determine the final sample size of 504 for the research.

A teacher-made test in Social Studies (TMTSS) served as the sole instrument for the research, comprising 50 objective question items addressing selected themes from the JSS3 Social Studies Scheme of Work for the second term. The instrument underwent face and content validity assessments by Social Studies specialists and other members of the Department of Social Science Education at Delta State University, Abraka.

The reliability of the instrument was established by conducting a pilot test using upper basic 9 (JSS3) social studies students in Delta Central Senatorial District, Delta State. Data generated were analysed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, which yielded a coefficient index of 0.85.

The researcher collected pre-test and post-test scores from the participants, yielding a mean performance score of 65.170 and a standard deviation of 8.579 on the pre-test. On the post-test, a mean performance score of 82.101 and a standard deviation of 8.417 were obtained. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were applied to answer the research question, while inferential statistics, such as t-tests, were used to assess the formulated hypothesis. The criterion mean is 2.50 to answer the research questions, while an alpha level of 0.05 was used to test the hypothesis.

Results

Research Question: What disparity exist in the academic performances of Upper-basic Social Studies students instructed through conventional methods compared to those taught with the cooperative learning strategy in Delta State?

Table 1: Showing Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of performances of Upper-basic Social Studies students taught with conventional methods and those taught with cooperative learning strategy.

Group	Pre-Test			Post-Test			Mean Difference
	N	$\bar{x}$	Std.	N	$\bar{x}$	Std.	
Conventional Methods	252	26.79	5.33	252	32.63	5.46	5.84
Cooperative learning	252	30.23	7.23	252	38.72	5.89	8.49
Mean Gained							2.65

Table 1 reveals the pre-test and post-test mean scores of Upper-basic Social Studies students taught with conventional and cooperative learning methods. It was revealed in the Table that students taught with the conventional learning method had a mean score of 26.79 and St.d of 5.33 and students taught with the cooperative learning method had a mean (x) score of 30.23, with a St.d of 7.23 at the pre-test level. While students taught with the conventional method had a mean score of 32.63 and St.d 5.46 and students taught with the cooperative method had a mean score of 38.72 and St.d of 5.89 at the post-test level. Therefore, the mean score for students taught with the conventional method is 5.84 and the mean score of students taught with the cooperative method is 8.49. This implies that students taught with the cooperative method had a mean gain of 2.65, indicating that students taught with the cooperative learning method performed better than students taught with the conventional method.

Test of Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no statistically significant disparity in the academic achievements of Upper-basic Social Studies students when comparing those instructed through conventional methods with those taught using the cooperative learning strategy in Delta State.

Table 2: Independent Sample t-test comparison of post-test performances of Upper-basic Social Studies students taught with conventional methods and those taught with cooperative learning strategy.

Group	Pre-Test			Post-Test			Df	t-Cal	Sig	Mean Difference	Decision
	N	$\bar{x}$	Std.	N	$\bar{x}$	Std.					
Conventional Methods	252	26.79	5.33	252	32.63	5.46	268	0.196	0.00	5.84	H ₀ is rejected
Cooperative learning	252	30.23	7.23	252	38.72	5.89				8.48	
Mean Gained										2.65	

The information presented in Table 2 indicates that the p-value of .001 is below the selected significant level $\alpha = 0.05$. Consequently, the research rejects the null hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that the mean ($\bar{x}$) of academic performances for Upper-basic Social Studies students instructed through conventional methods and those taught with the cooperative learning strategy is significantly different (i.e., $t(0.196) = 0.658, p < .001$). This conclusion is drawn as the mean ($\bar{x}$) score of Upper Social Studies students taught with the cooperative learning strategy is higher than those taught with conventional methods with a mean difference of 2.65. Therefore, students instructed through the Cooperative learning Strategy demonstrate significantly better performance in Upper-basic Social Studies compared to students taught with conventional methods in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

Outcomes presented in Table 1 illustrate the contrast in the mean ($\bar{x}$) scores between students instructed in Upper-basic Social Studies using Conventional Methods and those taught with the Cooperative learning strategy. Consequently, the findings indicate that students taught with the Cooperative learning strategy outperformed their counterparts taught with Conventional Methods. This suggests that prior to the implementation of the treatment (i.e., Cooperative learning Strategy), the academic performance of students was comparatively low. Thus, students instructed with the Cooperative learning strategy exhibit significantly superior performance in Upper Social Studies compared to those taught with Conventional Methods. This observation aligns with Marchetty's (2018) assertion that Cooperative learning is a commendable teaching approach, contributing to effective and efficient teaching. Additionally, the University of Marlborough (2019) found that engaging in team activities aids students in developing crucial communication and collaboration skills, preparing them for success both inside and outside the classroom. This aligns with Fredrick's (2008) perspective, who posited that Teamwork in education fosters a learner-centered learning approach and contributes to the progression of social skills in students. According to Fredrick, a classroom environment that encourages teamwork allows students to assert their authority over the material being studied.

Conclusion

Based on the findings obtained from the outcomes of the research, the research shows that Social Studies students in Upper-basic Schools taught using the Cooperative learning strategy performed better than those taught using the Conventional Method. The researcher concludes that Social Studies students were more actively engaged during instructional delivery as the Cooperative learning Strategy was used.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Educational institutions, particularly within the realm of upper-basic Social Studies, should contemplate the integration of the Cooperative learning Strategy into their instructional approaches as a means to augment students' academic performance.

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